

Sustainable and Corporate Social Responsibility: Global Economic Changes and Social Impacts

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Abstract

The need for raw materials, initiated by the industrial revolution in the 18th century, compelled humans to incessantly explore natural resources, resulting in significant ecological harm. Scientists are searching for methods to maintain a balance between productivity and the environment due to the growing population and the fast

depletion of natural resources. The behaviors that arose within the framework of this solution provided economic, ecological, and social benefits, establishing the basis for sustainable development. The idea of sustainable development was introduced in the literature at the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment in Stockholm in 1972. It was officially defined in the report "Our Common Future" issued in 1987. The notion of sustainable development, which entails fulfilling the requirements of the current generation without depriving the next generation of their needs, is synonymous with business sustainability. Corporate Social Responsibility, the primary component of corporate sustainability, has emerged in the business sector as a strategy to guarantee accountability and competitiveness. Furthermore, it distinguishes itself as a strategic notion in terms of delivering societal advantages. The objective of this research is to establish a connection between the principles of sustainable development, corporate sustainability, and corporate social responsibility, and to analyze these principles from a theoretical standpoint.

Keywords: Sustainability, Corporate Social Responsibility, Global Economy

1. Introduction

In TDK literature, the term sustainable is defined as "to continue" or "to ensure the continuation of a phenomenon", which aligns with the other meaning of the word "sustain". The term "unsustainable" is used to describe the opposite connotation of the phenomena represented as

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sustaining (Kılıç, 2012). Sustainability refers to the capacity to maintain and harmonize interactions between various ideas. The term sustainability, which is referred to as "sustainability" in English literature, was initially introduced into Turkish literature in 1987 as "sustainable development." This inclusion of the development aspect was made through the Brundtland Report titled "Our Common Future," prepared by the UN World Commission on Environment and Development [WCED]. The report mentioned above discusses the concept of sustainability, specifically in relation to sustainable development. According to the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED, 1987, p. 40), sustainable development is defined as "development that can maintain the current quality of life without jeopardizing the living conditions of future generations" (Şen, Kaya, & Alparslan, 2018). At the 2015 Paris Climate Summit, it was agreed upon to acknowledge a long-term temperature rise projection of 1.5 degrees Celsius compared to the pre-industrial period, as a measure to promote sustainability and mitigate the effects of global warming. This objective necessitates a confidential breakthrough and establishes the anticipation that governments should assume accountability inside the realm of sustainability. States and organizations are obligated to assume specific duties as a result of the choices made at the Paris Climate Summit and the sustainable development objectives. The European Union is spearheading this revolution, which has a direct influence on all nations and organizations. The notion of sustainability raises a significant concern for organizations and institutions. Thus, it may be said that there are significant uncertainties in the progression towards sustainability. The year is 2023, according to Yurdakul. The achievement of a sustainability phenomenon relies on the involvement of several aspects and a viewpoint that spans over a lengthy period of time. This phenomenon will occur when sustainability becomes ubiquitous, akin to a popular trend. Hence, it is important to establish constructive incentives for promoting sustainability inside enterprises or institutions. The factors on which motivation relies may differ across companies (Yurdakul, 2024). The 2024 Future of development Report, commissioned by the World Economic Forum and conducted by the TÜSİAD-Sabancı University Competition Forum, analyzes and evaluates the criteria for economic development in different nations. Past reports were often created in response to escalating rivalry. Currently, the standards and metrics are established based on the concepts of "Innovation, Inclusiveness, Sustainability, and Flexibility." The Future of Growth Report indicates that our country achieved a score of 44.9

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points, surpassing other comparable nations. The analysis assessed the quality of growth in 107 nations and highlighted that countries facing economic and geopolitical shocks may have a setback of 30 years in terms of development. Simultaneously, it has shown that economic equilibrium may be attained by prioritizing long-term sustainability, hence optimizing economic expansion (Nuyan, 2024).

2. Method

This study used a scanning methodology to examine the economic changes resulting from sustainability and corporate social responsibility on a worldwide scale. The aim was to uncover the impacts of these changes on both the economy and society. During the study phase, the researchers conducted a thorough review of the relevant literature and analyzed the many phases of sustainability, including its historical dimension, economic impacts, and social implications. Furthermore, there has been an analysis and interpretation of publications that highlight the influence of global sustainability on future prospects. During this procedure, attempts were made to find solutions to the following inquiries:

1. What are the effects of global economic changes on sustainability?
2. What are the sustainability-oriented strategies of companies and the effects of these strategies on economic performance and society?
3. What are the historical stages of sustainability and social responsibility? What stages have these concepts reached today?
4. What are the challenges facing the business world regarding sustainability and corporate social responsibility?

3. THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SUSTAINABILITY AND ECONOMIC CHANGE

3.1 Effects of Global Economic Changes on Sustainability

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The World Economic Development Commission has delineated three distinct dimensions of sustainability that are intricately interconnected.(Harris, 2000) (Mc Keown, Hopkins, Rizzi, & Chrystalbride, 2002, p. 8).

From an economic standpoint, a sustainable system must consistently generate commodities and services, effectively handle government relations and foreign debt, and prevent sectoral imbalances that might negatively impact agricultural and industrial output. Environmental sustainability refers to the need for resource systems to be renewable and the prevention of resource exploitation. Furthermore, it is important to adequately use non-renewable resources in order to replenish renewable resources and maintain resource equilibrium. Social sustainability may be defined as the maintenance of sufficient social services, including equitable distribution, education, healthcare, gender equality, and political transparency. As economies throughout the world advance, there is a corresponding growth in production technology and the use of raw materials and energy resources for manufacturing purposes. Manufacturers have placed significant emphasis on sustainability due to the paucity of resources and the high manufacturing costs. Furthermore, enterprises face the need to exhibit transparency and be held responsible to the public regarding the use and administration of natural resources. In economies that rely on production, the optimal use of resources and the mitigation of production-related pollution are closely interconnected. As resource use becomes more significant in emerging countries, the need to mitigate pollution becomes even more crucial. The phenomena described by Gatimbu, Ogada, Budambula, and Kariyuk (2018) is of utmost significance in the context of sustainability. Industrial economies have increasingly recognized the need of sustainability throughout time. Companies with more financial and operational resources has a greater likelihood of successfully competing in the marketplaces. By establishing environmental sustainability policies, the opportunity for competitiveness may be attained (Knight, Megicks, & Leenders, 2019). Businesses have access to a range of components that may be used for sustainability purposes.

3.1.1 Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)

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This research involves evaluating all aspects of a product, including its manufacture, distribution to the client, and consumption, as well as its effect on the environment and resources (Finnveden et al., 2009).

3.1.2 Life Cycle Costing (LCC)

The purpose is to analyze the economic impacts of the whole life cycle of a firm, including the production and consumption of its goods or services. The ISO 14000 series establishes a global benchmark by specifically addressing the environmental effects of this procedure (Hutchins & Sutherland, 2008).

3.2 The Effect of Companies' Sustainability-Focused Strategies on Economic Performance

Stakeholder Theory is widely recognized as one of the most impactful ideas in the realm of organizations' sustainability decision-making. The term "stakeholder" was coined by R. Edward in the 1980s. The idea of stakeholders, which influences the operational domains of organizations, is also influenced by the operational domains of the companies. Stakeholder theory is an ideology of capitalism that prioritizes the connections between corporations and its employees, customers, suppliers, and all individuals involved with the organization. This notion encompasses the principles of ethics, sustainability, and accountability. Furthermore, corporate social responsibility scrutinizes the ethical and value-based aspects of organizational management, akin to the principles of market economy and social contracts theory (Freeman, Harrison, Wicks, Parmar, & De Colle, 2010). Stakeholder theory assesses organizations based on their environmental variables, rather than only focusing on maximizing shareholder profits. Nevertheless, it embraces the perspective that all groups may get advantages from (Vander Laan Smith, Adhikâri, & Tondkar, 2005). According to this perspective, firms must consider stakeholder groups in order to guarantee their long-term viability. Companies have the opportunity to provide lasting value for stakeholders by implementing a sustainability plan that prioritizes ethical, social, environmental, economic, and cultural responsibilities (Ashrafi, Acciaro, Walker, Magnan, & Adams, 2019).

(Hüeske & Günther, 2021) They outlined sustainability-oriented initiatives in three parts. The first step entails the need for sustainability to be underpinned by innovation. This part requires an

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explanation of the sustainability aspects of the invention, including its influence on other sustainability dimensions, and the methods for measuring its performance upon implementation. During the second phase, it is crucial to identify both the potential advantages and challenges that may arise in relation to sustainable innovation. When doing a SWOT analysis, it is important to analyze the variables that contribute to strengths and barriers, and how these aspects impact sustainability.

The third stage involves the identification of implementation methods for sustainable innovations. When considering sustainability, it is important to prioritize which barriers should be addressed first, identify the variables that might contribute to success, and choose the appropriate methods to use at each stage of the process. Academician Bob Willard from the University of Toronto categorizes contemporary corporations into two distinct groupings. The first category consists of firms that prioritize sustainability as their foundational principle. Both of these firms are advancing towards a prosperous economic venture and have the objective of being advantageous to the environment. The second category of firms comprises those that have fully incorporated sustainability into all aspects of their operations. Their intention was to be advantageous to the Earth. They attain their objectives by establishing themselves as a prosperous corporate entity. In response to client demand, the British firm Marks & Spencer created a strategy known as "Plan A" in 2007. The phrase "Because There Is No Plan B!" was introduced after this title. Based on this comprehension, the firm has embarked on a mission to become the most environmentally conscious retailer globally. Consequently, it has identified the crucial principles of addressing climate change, minimizing waste, promoting sustainable use of raw materials, supporting fair trade, and prioritizing customer wellness for both itself and its stakeholders. After a 4-year period, the positive strategies used by the Marks & Spencer brand were evident. In the 2011 annual report, it was seen that the firm saw a net value growth of 70 million pounds (Nuyan, 2024).

4. CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY AND ITS SOCIAL IMPACT

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The discussion around the notion of corporate social responsibility emerged during the Great Depression of 1929 in the United States. Subsequently, throughout the 1960s, it started to gain traction in the corporate realm, as well as in legal, political, and economic spheres, ultimately becoming a significant notion. Since the 1990s, the notion has gained significant importance and has been widely used in many aspects of life worldwide (Yönet, 2005, p. 239). The citation (Friedman, 1970) Social responsibility refers to the obligation of enterprises to perform their economic tasks within the boundaries of the law. Corporate social responsibility is a widely acknowledged notion that encompasses the economic, legal, ethical, and volunteer actions that society expects firms to engage in at a given period (Carrol, 1979, p. 497).

4.1 Social Responsibilities of Companies and the Effects of These Responsibilities on Society

(Carrol, 1979) He examined the concept of corporate social responsibility under four separate headings. These; They are Economic Responsibility, Legal Responsibility, Ethical Responsibility and Voluntary Responsibility.

- Economic Responsibility: To be profitable for the company's shareholders and to maintain profitability, to be an employer and to produce products that ensure customer satisfaction.
- Legal Responsibility: Complying with the obligations imposed by the law.
- Ethical Responsibility: To ensure ethical, correct and fair business without harming the environment and humanity.
- Volunteer Responsibilities: Sacrificing time and money for any work done to provide unrequited benefit to society.

In the modern period, firms have expanded their social duties and interactions beyond the realm of business by incorporating social and environmental concerns into their operations. It is evident that firms engage in social responsibility in addition to pursuing financial success. Businesses have a crucial role in taking on social duties due to the rise in environmental issues, social and legal concerns, and economic disparities. Consumers and investors anticipate that corporations would not only achieve success but also fulfill their obligations while being cognizant of their social

responsibilities. The significant effects of corporations on facilitating social transformation are as follows:

4.1.1 Transition to Green Energy

Energy sector companies switch to renewable energy sources instead of using fossil fuels and thus contribute to sustainability.

4.1.2 Social Entrepreneurship

Some companies integrate social problems into their business model and use the income they earn to solve social problems.

4.1.3 Employee Rights and Fair Labor Practices

This issue is one of the most important concepts in companies' sustainability and corporate social responsibility practices today. The importance of increasing workability motivation in the workplace increases over time. Companies indirectly convey to their customers the importance they attach to employee rights.

4.1.4 Campaigns for Social Problems

Companies activate many projects and practices to draw attention to social problems. The “Daddy, Send Me to School” project, initiated by Doğan Publishing Group in 2005, was initiated to ensure that girls who were not sent to school were enrolled in school. With this project, significant scholarship opportunities were provided to send girls to school.

4.1.5 Sustainable Supply Chain Practices

It shows an environmentally friendly approach in companies' resource use, product delivery or operation of any service unit (Demirkaya & Yardım , 2024).

4.2 The Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility on Company Reputation and Consumer Preferences

Businesses are establishments that need meticulous administration. Hence, strategic components are used to enhance the business image. One of these approaches is the notion of corporate social responsibility. Corporate social responsibility is seen as a strategic objective for firms to adjust to competitive circumstances and ensure their long-term viability. (Maden, Arıkan, Teki, & Kantur, 2012). Businesses that demonstrate awareness of their obligations, prioritize social responsibility concerns, and consistently integrate them into their operations are seen favorably by society. According to Karatepe and Ozan (2017, p. 93), this greatly enhances the standing of firms. Businesses should effectively communicate to their stakeholders the investments they make in order to actively contribute to their community and environment. Businesses must execute these procedures with great precision in order to form relationships with the public and build a strong company reputation and recognition (Bıçakçı, 2016, p. 54). The 2007 research done by Hillenbrand and Money, which explores the correlation between social responsibility and company reputation, may be found in contemporary literature. Based on this research, it was shown that there is a direct and positive correlation between the two notions. It has been established that company reputation has a beneficial impact on the behavior of consumers, employees, and investors. The citation for the source is Hillenbrand & Money, 2007. (Öztürk, 2021). Hence, when a corporation prioritizes corporate social responsibility and incorporates it into its operations, it elicits favorable reactions from its consumers and substantially boosts its sales. The corporate social responsibility policies of organizations might be seen as an asset in the eyes of consumers or customers. This perspective influences customers' sense of product quality, leading to brand loyalty and favorable brand awareness (Çiftçioğlu & Gök, 2018).

5. SUSTAINABILITY AND CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY IN THE CONTEXT OF ECONOMIC HISTORY

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The term "sustainability" was first used in the book "Guide to Wild Tree Cultivation" "[Sylvicultura Oeconomica]", authored by Hans Carl Von Carlowitz, a German Mine Operator, in 1713. However, the book was not published until 1732. The book discusses the environmental harm caused by logging woods in the Saxony region for use in mining operations. It also introduces the term "nachhaltigkeit," which refers to the concept of sustainability in forest conservation (Wiersum, 1995). Carlowitz's pioneering work, which introduced the notion of sustainability in relation to forestry, is often regarded as the inception of the field of sustainable development. He highlighted the imbalance between resources and needs in sustainability, tracing it back to the industrial revolution. He proposed the idea of "preservation of stocks" and brought the notion of "stock management" into the present day (Vehkamaki, 2005). According to Vehkamaki (2005, p. 37), scholars who analyze the idea of sustainability from a historical viewpoint contend that it has a long-standing history and assert that it is referenced in the book of Genesis in the Bible. He asserts that the notion emerged in literature around the 1700s. The concept of sustainability gained prominence in the 1760s via the research conducted by German scholars known as "Management of Forests". Georg Ludwig Hartig's essay "Tax Regulations and Description of Forests" in 1805 brought attention to sustainability. It is evident that sustainability has been a significant aspect of forest management for the last century (Duerr & Duerr, 1975). Renewable natural resources refer to products that are specifically associated with the forestry and fishing professions. Lélé defines sustainability of these resources as the exploitation of the resource stock at a pace that is lower than its natural growth rate (Lélé, 2007, p. 1102). Hence, to discuss the sustainability of the wood stock in the forest, it is necessary to examine the correlation between the size of the stock and the pace at which trees grow.

5.1 Evolution of Sustainability Efforts in Economic History

In 1972, the Club of Rome issued research. The paper titled "Limits to Growth" emerged as a pioneering and significant contribution to the literature on sustainable development. This research, conducted by scholars affiliated with the "Massachusetts Institute of Technology", began in 1965 and was completed in 1972 (Meadows, Randers, Dennis, & Behrens III, 1972). Furthermore, in 1980, the "Union for the Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources" was established,

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comprising of the United Nations Environment Program [UNEP], World Wildlife Fund [WWF], UN Food and Agriculture Organization [FAO], and UN Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO]. The research paper titled "World Conservation Strategy" was delivered. The Brundland Report, issued in 1987, introduced and popularized the notion of sustainability. In recent years, the growing global environmental issues have highlighted the significance of the economy-environment interaction. Consequently, the topic of sustainability has become a recurring item on the agenda. This paper covers three main subjects: "fundamental necessities, ecological development, and sustainable utilization". The final statement known as Agenda 21, which was accepted at the Rio Earth Summit in 1992 and the 2002 Earth Summit in Johannesburg, South Africa, established the decision to execute growth and development plans that would include both environmental and social sustainability.

5.2 Development and Change of Corporate Social Responsibility Throughout History

The 19th century saw several inventions that not only revolutionized the globe but also gave rise to employment-related disputes between employers and workers. The advent of factories in the USA brought out concerns over working conditions and employment, particularly highlighting the disparity in the employment of children and women. This topic gained significant attention (Gedik, 2020). Corporate Social Responsibility did not acquire significance until the 1950s, despite the occurrence of the Great Depression in 1929 and World War II in the early 1940s. The thesis titled "The Necessity of Businesses Holding Responsibility for Humanity as a Result of Their Activities", proposed by Frank W. Abrams, a former executive at Standard Oil Company in New Jersey in 1951, led to the global recognition and inclusion of corporate social responsibility as a prominent issue. Howard R. Bowen is credited with introducing the notion of Modern Corporate Social Responsibility in his book "Social Responsibilities Of The Businessman" in 1953. As a result of this influential work, Bowen is widely recognized as the founder of CSR (Ashraf, Magnan, Adams, & Walker, 2020, p. 3). In this book, Bowen provided a definition of Corporate Social Responsibility as the act of manufacturers assuming responsibility for making judgments within the boundaries of this policy and adhering to business procedures that align with the objectives and principles of mankind. In the 1960s, academics took a new approach to Corporate

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Social Responsibility and focused on addressing the issues and needs of society. During this age, the primary objective of Corporate Social Responsibility was to fulfill the dual task of ensuring financial profitability while also addressing social responsibilities towards society. The potential advantages that Corporate Social Responsibility might provide to the firm have been overlooked. The economic advantages of implementing the notion of corporate social responsibility in enterprises became evident throughout the 1970s. Corporate Social Performance (CSP) was formed as an extension of corporate social responsibility. Its purpose is to address societal pressures faced by corporations. The CSP idea, known as KSS2 in the literature, was proposed by Robert W. Ackerman, as stated by Frederick (Ashraf, Magnan, Adams, & Walker, 2020, pp. 3-4). Preston established the Social Response Matrix in 1977. The objective of this matrix is to guarantee that corporations effectively address and handle social issues. The matrix was established based on the premise that managers adhere to the corporate social involvement procedure.

The matrix is explained as follows:

- i. A location awareness and recognition
- ii. Analysis and planning
- iii. Response in terms of policy development
- iv. APPLICATION

The survey tools of Clarkson (1995, p. 93) were used to apply this analytical insight. In 1979, Carrol enhanced Preston's 1975 model by creating a novel framework that incorporates corporate social aims and economic ambitions inside the CSR2+CSR integrity. Carrol's CSR Model was developed and used throughout the 1980s and 1990s. The 3P CSR model developed by Wartick and Cochran is described as a model that encompasses principles, policies, and processes (Abe & Ruanglikhitkul, 2013). The introduction of environmental legislation in the United Kingdom and the United States throughout the 1980s heightened the significance of conservation and sustainable development concerns. CSR had growth until the 1970s, but it evolved further in the 1980s with the introduction of concepts such as stakeholder theory, sustainability, corporate citizenship, and corporate social activities. In 1991, scholar Donna J. Wood did a study that examined the outcomes

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of research on corporate social responsibility (CSR) and applied the four categories of corporate responsibility previously established by Carrol to three different business sectors.

In 1991, Carroll undertook a fresh investigation on Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). The research, known as the "Corporate Social Responsibility Pyramid," outlines the economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic obligations of organizations. Institutions have a social obligation that includes meeting society's economic, legal, ethical, and common sense expectations. According to reports, it was widely recognized by the 2000s that CSR has gained significant importance as a strategic idea for organizations (Maura-Leitte & Padgett, 2011). The notion of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is now widely acknowledged as the Triple Bottom Line (TBL). This variation of the notion emphasizes the need for enterprises to prioritize both the well-being of mankind and the planet that humanity inhabits, in addition to their economic motivation. In light of the impact of the digital realm, several firms use a strategy centered on the accumulation and utilization of extensive data. These firms have incorporated themselves into the digital realm to provide a framework for elucidating the notion of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). They do this by translating their economic, environmental, and social performance into measurable data and interpreting it via the processes of data collection, analysis, and decision-making. By adopting this approach, organizations are able to not only focus on generating profit, but also to elucidate the cause-and-effect link between stakeholders and the profit component (Jhawar & Gupta, 2017, p. 108).

6. COMING CHALLENGES AND FUTURE STRATEGIES

6.1 Key Challenges in Sustainability and Corporate Social Responsibility

In our contemporary society, both natural and man-made catastrophes such as the climate crisis, armed conflict-induced famine, natural disasters, scarcity of food and water, disparities in wealth, and gender inequality exert immense pressure on mankind, ultimately resulting in loss of life. These challenges are insurmountable for both a state and a firm. In the present day, it is essential for firms or enterprises to participate in these events, which were previously addressed via the collaboration of governments and non-governmental organizations. Examining the social aspect of the COVID-19 pandemic, it becomes evident that society also have certain expectations from corporations (Gönen, 2024). It is essential for institutions and organizations to adopt a balanced approach in addressing the emission of greenhouse gases as part of their sustainability and corporate social responsibility requirements. The growing prominence of the "Carbon Neutral Company" idea worldwide has redefined the rivalry among corporations and organizations in terms of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). Furthermore, the use of wind and solar energy to generate kinetic and potential energy has highlighted the imperative need for substantial technical investment by corporations. When adopting CSR practices, institutions and enterprises should examine their own goal and vision. Implementing a corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiative that goes against the core purpose of a firm might undermine the authenticity of its brand image. Therefore, firms must exercise great caution while conducting a CSR initiative. According to Peter Drucker's statement "You cannot manage what you do not measure," it is crucial to assess corporate social responsibility (CSR) policies and their effect (Zak, 2024). Furthermore, the adoption of a transparent management style by organizations not only demonstrates their prioritization of workers, society, and consumers, but also serves as an indication of their future business practices. Hence, the implementation of a transparent management style by corporations has significant relevance in terms of the application of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). Capitalism has significant influence on the majority of economies worldwide. The correlation between capitalism and the free market prompts inquiries on whether phase of the economic management process can really be characterized as free. It is important to acknowledge that the

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free market economy's use of natural resources based on free market principles poses significant challenges in implementing sustainability. Carbon pricing has never been a prominent topic since the broad adoption of capitalism. The unrestricted use of fossil fuels during production and sales has resulted in the emission of carbon into the atmosphere, leading to significant consequences (in terms of health, economics, and environment) that mankind continues to bear. Not accounting for this expense in the corporate sector results in significant financial hardships for nations and societies when implementing and operating sustainability programs. If the income disparity and tax injustice resulting from capitalism are not effectively tackled, the provision of carbon prices will not be equitable. This problem is a priority in terms of sustainability and has to be addressed promptly. Research in the business sector has shown that the majority of CEOs and leaders express a strong commitment to sustainability and corporate social responsibility (CSR). However, these practices are often ranked lower, in the third or fourth position, on their list of business priorities. According to Winston's (2020) study, CEOs who have prior expertise in sustainability and corporate social responsibility (CSR) have a higher level of concern for this problem. Hence, by appealing to the CEOs' emotions about sustainability and corporate social responsibility (CSR), we may guarantee that this procedure will be granted more significance. The disparity in economic distribution across communities and people indicates a prevailing preference among global customers for inexpensive and environmentally unfriendly items, as opposed to retail products. While individuals may argue for the need of selecting ecologically sustainable items when expressing their preferences, sales figures from corporations indicate that this is not really happening in reality. Due to global economic challenges and consumer demand for inexpensive and ecologically harmful items, manufacturers are mindful of these factors and persist in producing products that are not environmentally friendly. This condition has detrimental impacts on sustainability and corporate social responsibility (CSR).

7. Conclusion

Ever since the 1972 Stockholm Conference, the concept of sustainable development has been more significant in both corporate and national management strategies. The primary paradigm of the life

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cycle is the capacity to transmit limited resources in nature to an endless number of generations, as defined in economics. This term is intricately linked to sustainability.

The notion of sustainable development, including economic, social, and ecological dimensions, emerged in the corporate management discourse during the early 1990s. Businesses or businesses have developed a keen interest in addressing social issues alongside their primary goal of generating profit, and have therefore initiated initiatives in this domain. The notion of sustainability is now linked not just to ecological policies but also to other actions undertaken by corporations. Corporate sustainability, a more encompassing iteration of sustainability, places significant obligations on institutions and organizations to ensure the ongoing profitability and operations of their business. As a result, concepts like responsibility and transparent management have arisen. These truths are the fundamental principles of business sustainability. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a closely connected matter to the notion of sustainability. CSR, or Corporate Social Responsibility, encompasses all the activities and initiatives undertaken by corporations and individuals to contribute to the betterment of society. This notion is not only essential for all firms in the present day, but it also serves as a competitive factor. Over the last three decades, corporations have essentially reached a consensus on the notion of sustainable development. Companies assert their commitment to promoting sustainable development for society by implementing social responsibility practices, as well as fulfilling economic, social, and ecological responsibilities. Countless multinational corporations, as well as numerous local businesses, globally oversee international commerce. While these corporations play a significant role in the development of the nations they operate in, they also have four crucial obligations towards these countries:

- Economy-dimensional responsibility; Responsibility of companies to produce efficiency and profit,
- Liability with a legal dimension; Responsibility to operate in accordance with country and world law,
- Ethical responsibility; Responsibility to behave in accordance with social rules beyond the law,

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- Responsibility with social dimension; It is the responsibility of volunteering to contribute to solving social problems.

When analyzing the aforementioned components of duty, the encompassing notion is corporate social responsibility. CSR, or Corporate Social Responsibility, is a concept that addresses societal issues and entails adopting language that meets societal standards. It is a phenomenon that brings satisfaction to workers, consumers, stakeholders, and society as a whole. Operating with sustainability awareness is a crucial practice for firms when assessed in terms of corporate social responsibility (CSR). In order to achieve sustainable production, it is necessary to refrain from depleting resources that future generations will rely on, avoid causing damage to the health of the present generation, and preserve the continuity of life for both society and future generations. This phenomenon serves as the foundation of sustainability. The evaluation of firms' adherence to their pledges to society or consumers is also conducted within the context of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and is considered a significant obligation. Adhering to contracts, promptly paying debts and employee salaries are crucial aspects of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) implementation. Upon observing the global landscape, it becomes evident that firms are actively adopting corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives that include ecological, social, and economic aspects. They reinforce their brand by promoting sustainability via social responsibility initiatives. The possibility of holding individuals accountable is facilitated by an approach to management that is characterized by transparency. This, in turn, allows for a methodical approach to dealing with nature and limited resources. The favorable perception that this mindset creates for corporations is associated with the corporate social responsibility (CSR) strategy, and it also significantly enhances the firms' economic performance.

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